

Title

Results of A survey of macroscopic beach dependent invertebrates and attempted comparison between beaches experiencing different levels of motorized recreation.

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15 February 2019

Abstract

Sandy beaches with reduced or complete prohibitions on vehicle use were identified for sampling in consultation with Nantucket Conservation Foundation (NCF) and Nantucket Islands Land Bank (NILB) staff. Very few species and families were documented. Detectable recreational impacts were overwhelmed by the effects of relatively recent repeat storm events that drastically altered beach morphology and ecology.

Introduction

In 2014 I conducted a field trip at Eel Point Beach for the NBI during which a group of conference attendees collected live specimens of all the invertebrates they could find; first on a beach where vehicles were prohibited and then on a beach experiencing heavy traffic. The specimens were photographed and identified to species level. Twelve species in seven families were observed on the vehicle free beach and 0 species were detected on the heavily used beach. This effort attempted to expand surveyed areas to other beaches where beach fauna could be documented.

Methods and study sites

Sampling methods were exclusively hand and net collection. While pit fall trapping was proposed, high winds and low diversity documented, negated the efficacy of pit fall trapping.

Eel Point, located on the Northwest end of the Island, is a highly dynamic beach bordered by Nantucket Sound and Madaket Harbor. It was more diverse morphologically and ecologically than any of the other beaches visited and was sampled more frequently.

Sheep Pond. The washover fan at Sheep Pond is moving rapidly inland. It was considered too short and small in areal extent to be included in repeat samplings.

Hummock Pond, Sesachacha, Squam Pond, Madequecham and Tom Nevers Beaches.

All of these sites with southern exposures were found to have recently experienced high energy erosion events.

Low Beach. One of the only Atlantic facing beaches that is accreting, two visits resulted in very few species of invertebrates documented.

Results.

Three collecting visits on four days between May and October added only a few species to the list compiled in 2014.

The hairy collared tiger beetle, *Cicindela, hirticollis* was observed only at Eel Point where a population of several hundred is evident. The *C. marginata*, salt marsh tiger beetle, population also numbers in the hundreds of individuals and was encountered only at Eel Point, the only salt marsh habitat sampled.

Cremastocheilus harrisii was observed at Madequecham, an inquiline of the genus *Formica* ants and probably wide spread on Nantucket.

Discussion

The failure to detect a diverse, well developed invertebrate community is attributed to recent disturbances in the form of storms that removed much of the sediment comprising the intertidal zone and serves as the substrate for many invertebrates that burrow in sand for a portion of their life cycles.

Many common beach dwelling invertebrates including species that have been collected historically in Nantucket were not observed in 2018.

This lack of diversity observed is not atypical of disturbance dependent habitats following major perturbations.

Recommendations

Similar surveys, especially if there is a hiatus in major disturbances, could be performed in the future or specimens collected by staff and visitors could be sent to me for identification.

Acknowledgments

Karen C. Beattie and Libby Buck of the Nantucket Conservation Foundation supplied advice and transportation. Transportation, advice and housing were also supplied by Rachael Freeman and summer staff of the Nantucket Islands Land Bank. The Nantucket Field Station offered housing which was not required for this project in 2018.

Eel Point showing eroded dunes and multiple wrack lines.

Low Beach showing berm, coarse sediments and depauperate flora.

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Table 1

Nantucket Beach Invertebrates Documented in 2018

Order	Family	Genus and Species	Comments
Coleoptera	Tenebrionidae	<i>Phaleria testaceous</i>	Flightless, vulnerable
		<i>Cicindela hirticollis</i>	vulnerable
		<i>C. marginata</i>	salt marsh tiger beetle
	Scarabaeidae	<i>Exolama orientalis</i>	introduced turf feeder
		<i>Cremastocheilus harrisii</i>	ant eating scarab, inquiline
		<i>Spilodiscus arcuatus</i>	carrion feeder
	Histeridae	<i>Hypocaccus dimidiatipennis</i>	predator
		<i>Sphenophorus v. venatus</i>	grass feeder
		<i>Agraphus bellicus</i>	flightless, scavenger?
	Curculionidae	<i>Philopodon plagiatum</i>	introduced
		<i>Aphilanthops sp</i>	predatory wasp
		<i>Sphex sp.</i>	predatory wasp
	Hymenoptera	Crabronidae	<i>Coelopa frigida</i>
Diptera	Coelopidae	<i>Arctosa littoralis</i>	beach wolf spider
Araneae	Lycosidae	<i>Pardosa milvina</i>	shore spider